

Contributi/5

What is a Paradigm?

A Brief Inquiry on the Normativity and Visibility of Models in Antiquity

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This essay explores the multifaceted concept of *paradeigma* (παράδειγμα) in ancient thought, tracing its semantic, pragmatic, and philosophical dimensions across a range of contexts – from artisanal and architectural practices to Platonic metaphysics, rhetorical theory, and moral education. Anchored in the dual axes of *normativity* and *visibility*, the study argues that paradigms function as normative references whose authority depends on their recognizability and exemplarity within specific cultural, practical, and pedagogical frameworks. By analyzing key ancient sources, including Plato's *Timaeus*, *Republic*, *Sophist*, and *Politicus*, Aristotle's *Rhetoric*, and the rhetorical writings of Isocrates, the essay reconstructs how paradigms guide action, shape learning, and support ethical deliberation. Whether as models of production, heuristic tools in philosophical inquiry, rhetorical instruments in deliberative speech, or moral exempla in political discourse, paradigms act as dynamic devices that mediate between past and present, offering culturally intelligible standards for imitation, judgment, and decision-making. Rather than defining a fixed essence, *paradeigmata* reflect historically embedded practices of comparison and exemplarity, emphasizing their essential role in the moral and epistemic formation of individuals and communities.

Introduction

The aim of this essay is to construct a semantic map of the various meanings of the term *paradeigma* (παράδειγμα) through an examination of selected ancient historical and philosophical texts, offering an overview of its usage mainly – but not exclusively – during the 5th and 4th centuries BCE. My goal is to analyze the significance of the term in relation to its philosophical reinterpretation, ultimately developing a theoretical model for understanding how a paradigm functions and what it fundamentally is. Broadly speaking, the term *paradeigma* encompasses a range of interpretations and meanings: it may

denote a model crafted by an architect, sculptor, or painter, or a sample that serves as a reference or standard for the production of a material object; it can refer to a precedent – an action from the past that conveys a moral lesson, often illustrated through historical parallels; it may describe an individual deemed worthy of imitation (or, if an anti-model, an individual that serves as a negative reference point, illustrating behaviors, characteristics, or outcomes to be avoided or discouraged); it may represent a concrete instance of an abstract concept, rule, or prescription. Pragmatically, it can function as a method of argument or a rhetorical device aimed at persuasion; and, finally, it may serve as an educational and didactic tool, offering the interlocutor a familiar reference point that aids in grasping a more complex and unfamiliar concept.

Although these meanings may seem diverse, a closer examination of their contexts reveals a certain coherence. Two categories may help clarify this unified meaning: “normativity” and “visibility.” A *paradeigma* is generally a specific entity – animate or inanimate, crafted or natural – or an event, typically from the past, that holds normative and implicit or explicit prescriptive value for another individual or collective. This normative quality underpins its moral dimension: a *paradeigma* can only emerge where practical guidance is needed. *Paradeigmata* are not “given” by nature; they respond to practical needs, serving as “practical quiddities” that direct production, learning, the imitation of specific actions, or deterrence. The normative value of a *paradeigma* may pertain to a particular situation or individual, but it does not universally apply to everyone. Being a paradigm does not define the essence of a thing; instead, it reflects the practical significance that this entity holds for those who seek to use it as a model. The effectiveness of a paradigm’s normative role is realized through comparison and the recognition or reproduction of similarities. A *paradeigma* serves as a standard, criterion, or measure, facilitating comparisons between different realities to identify, create, or replicate a resemblance. The process of comparison triggered by *paradeigmata* goes beyond mere measurement; they offer a meaningful reference that informs action, decision-making, and a range of practical tasks.

The concept of “visibility,” which helps define *paradeigmata*, operates on two levels. First, some entities derive their normative authority from being prominently displayed in public or private spaces – such as laws or decrees inscribed on stone, statues, memorials in the city or temples, or models and samples showcased in workshops or markets – or from being highlighted, recalled, commended, and glorified in rhetorical speeches as representative events or individuals. Here, visibility and normativity reinforce each other; for something to hold paradigmatic influence, it must be or become distinctly visible, and this visibility, in turn, amplifies its normative power. Therefore, what is most visible naturally becomes exemplary.

Second, visibility implies familiarity: *paradeigmata* exert their normative influence most effectively when they are accessible and recognizable to those they intend to guide. For example, in learning, a *paradeigma* must be sufficiently

familiar for learners to relate it to new or complex concepts. Similarly, a rhetorician aiming to persuade by referencing recent historical events will rely on those that are widely acknowledged by the audience. By contrast, a *paradeigma* that is obscure or concealed risks losing its normative impact. Visibility is thus crucial to a paradigm's effectiveness, as it reinforces both relevance and authority. These characteristics impart a specific temporality to *paradeigmata*: they lead from the known to the unknown, from past to future, serving as didactic tools for assessing human historicity through a moral lens. In this way, the past – its events, deeds, and especially virtuous figures – becomes a resource for guiding one's actions in the present. What is made visible from the past holds existential or practical relevance for current decision-making. In historical narratives, human historicity is often framed through *exempla*, as knowledge of past events fosters informed deliberation in the present.

To explore the connections among these elements, the essay is structured into five sections. The first section examines the original meaning of the term, particularly its significance within architectural and artisanal practices (§1). The following sections focus on the philosophical meaning of the term within Plato's philosophy: first, by addressing the role of *paradeigmata* in Plato's metaphysics (§2), where Forms hold a paradigmatic value for sensible realities, conceived as images that resemble these models; then, by considering its function as a philosophical tool and exercise (§3), characterized by a primarily didactic and dialectical role. The subsequent section (§4) discusses Aristotle's treatment of the example within the context of *Rhetoric*, emphasizing the practical and persuasive power of the *paradeigma*: examples may serve as a form of argumentation aimed at persuasion, guiding action and deliberation within a specific temporal framework. The final section (§5) examines the *exemplum virtutis* and the "paradigmatic" view of history, understood as a repertoire of exemplary individuals to which one ought to look for guidance in orienting their conduct.

1. Replicability: the normativity of models in craftsmanship and architectural practices

The term παράδειγμα is deeply intertwined with both architectural and artisanal practices. Etymologically, it derives from the verb παραδείκνυμι, which primarily means "to exhibit side by side" and also encompasses the meaning of "to compare." This linguistic relationship suggests that a *paradeigma* can be understood as a standard or model – a prototype that serves as a reference for replication or an image intended to be reproduced in accordance with it (πρὸς τὸ παράδειγμα). It acts as an object against which the final product is evaluated. Thus, *paradeigmata* were a reference point in the processes of creation,

replication, and production.¹ Evidence from the 5th and 4th century BCE attests to the use of the term in epigraphic sources, specifically within architectural and artisanal contexts. Here, *paradeigmata* were created for the construction of various components – especially decorative details – serving as standards for replication. In these practices, the faithful reproduction of a paradigm’s form was of paramount importance, ensuring consistency across the production process².

However, the concept of replicability alone does not fully capture the complexity of the term. A *paradeigma* embodies a normative dimension that extends beyond mere reproduction of an original. *Paradeigmata* do not relate to replicas as originals relate to images; instead, they signify a connection between a model for a practice (in this case a productive practice) and those responsible for creating works in its likeness. In other words, *paradeigmata* relate not to the replicas themselves, but to those responsible for producing them. While the model is itself a crafted object, its true significance lies not simply in its status as the “original” in a replication process, but in its role as a guiding principle for artisans, providing the standards and direction necessary to faithfully execute the work³. *Paradeigmata* embody a kind of contract of confidence between the desired outcome and the concrete work of artisans. By commissioning a *paradeigma*, the essential criteria for the production are established; in this way, a paradigm exerts an authoritative influence over those responsible for the concrete production of replicas⁴. This normative function is particularly evident in the practice of compensating third parties for the creation of models, ensuring that artisans could align their production with the expectations set by the commissioner⁵.

¹ Cf. J. Onians, *Idea and Product: Potter and Philosopher in Classical Athens*. «Journal of Design History», 4/2 (1991), p. 68; R. Patterson, *Image and Reality in Plato’s Metaphysics*, Indianapolis 1985, pp. 13-16. The term, from this point of view, can be compared to τύπος; see A. Von Blumenthal, *ΤΥΠΟΣ und ΠΑΡΑΔΕΙΓΜΑ*, «Hermes», 63/1 (1928), pp. 391-414.

² J. J. Pollitt, *The Ancient View of Greek Art*, New Haven 1974, pp. 204-214, collects the occurrences of the term παράδειγμα in the epigraphic material from the 4th and 3rd centuries BCE and in literary sources relevant to the study of the arts in the ancient world. The types of models for architectural and artistic practice are varied, but in every case, they involve ornamental details or parts of buildings: models of fences, decorations, architectural ornaments, fountain spouts, moldings, pins, capitals, or tiles.

³ Cf. Pl. *Plt.* 259e8-11: the architect does not directly build the structure, but rather oversees those who do the work; he provides knowledge, not manual labor (Καὶ γὰρ ἀρχιτέκτων γε πᾶς οὐκ αὐτὸς ἐργατικὸς ἀλλ’ ἐργατῶν ἄρχων [...] Παρεχόμενός γέ που γνῶσιν ἀλλ’ οὐ χειρουργίαν).

⁴ Cf. J. J. Coulton, *Ancient Greek Architects at Work: Problems of Structure and Design*, Ithaca (N.Y.), pp. 54-57.

⁵ Payments for the construction of models are documented, as seen in IG 4².102 A 150-151; 102 B 296; 102 B 303 (Epidaurus, 4th century BCE). Cf. also IG 2².1678 A 10ff. References to παραδείγματα appear in the context of building plans (συγγραφαί), such as that of the Σκευοθέκη by Philo in Piraeus, although it is likely that παραδείγματα were not generally considered as “scale” models (cf. J.J. Coulton, *Ancient Greek Architects at Work*, p. 57): IG 2².1668.87 (πρὸς τὸ παράδειγμα ποιήσας); 94-95 (ταῦτα ἅπαντα ἐξεργάσσονται οἱ μισθωσάμενοι κατὰ τὰς συγγραφὰς καὶ πρὸς τὰ μέτρα καὶ πρὸς τὸ παράδειγμα). The architect provided practical instructions through the συγγραφαί (the same term also designated contracts), which described the arrangement of the building and the guidelines to follow for its construction. He also supplied a list of measurements (μέτρα) and visual models of some of its

The normative authority of a paradigm is closely tied to its visibility. For a *paradeigma* to serve effectively as a rule or standard, it must be rendered accessible and evident to those who are meant to use or to look at it; it needs to be displayed or exhibited in a way that facilitates easy adherence. As mentioned, the verb παραδείκνυμι conveys the idea of comparison and implies the acts of showing and displaying (δεικνύσθαι) alongside (παρά) the object to be produced. A paradigmatic object derives its normative power through a special kind of visibility – by being shown, exhibited, and demonstrated, it compels comparison and provides a tangible standard for alignment⁶.

This interrelation between visibility and normativity is particularly evident in the pottery trade during the Archaic and Classical periods. Merchants acted as intermediaries between workshops, particularly in Athens and Corinth, and the expanding market for such goods. To facilitate this exchange, they used samples (δείγματα)⁷ that were displayed at markets and events, allowing buyers to directly compare and evaluate the products⁸. These visible samples mediated between the demand of the market and the production in workshops, guiding artisans toward the production of goods that met specific expectations⁹. In addition, *paradeigmata* were likely displayed within the workshops themselves, allowing artisans to closely observe and study them¹⁰. In this way, a *paradeigma* functions as both a visible and authoritative reference, guiding the production process while ensuring the final product meets the desired standards of quality and coherence.

parts (though likely not the entire building before the Hellenistic period: cf. IG 11.2.165.17; although cf. Hdt. 5.62.16-17) through παραδείγματα. Cf. S. Kostof, *The Practice of Architecture in the Ancient World: Egypt and Greece*, in id. (ed.), New York 1977, pp. 13-16. As noted by J. J. Coulton, *Ancient Greek Architects at Work*, p. 57, in the case of decorative details, παραδείγματα were commissioned from third parties, while it is unclear whether the architects themselves produced the models. Nevertheless, it was the architect's duty to provide the models alongside the συγγραφαί. It is also possible that the models were graphic in nature (cf. IG11.2.161 A 75-76).

⁶Regarding the paradigmatic value of visibility in its public and social dimension (understood as the exposure and “spectacularization” of an individual who has worked on themselves in the public space), I refer to the essay by A. Lucci, “Techniques de visibilité,” in A. De Cesaris & G. Lingua (eds.), Paris 2021, pp. 51-66, which frames the issue within the context of ascetic practices.

⁷With the same meaning as “sample,” see also Herodotus's testimony about wooden models of mummies (2.86.2-4: Οὔτοι, ἐπεάν σφι κομισθῆ νεκρός, δεικνύουσι τοῖσι κομίσασι παραδείγματα νεκρῶν ξύλινα, τῆ γραφῆ μεμιμημένα).

⁸The Δεῖγμα, for example, was a section of the port of Piraeus specifically designated for the exhibition of works to clients (Xen. *Hell.* 5.1.21).

⁹J. Onians, *Idea and Product*, pp. 66-67.

¹⁰*Ibid.*, p. 68.

2. *Paradeigmata* in Plato's metaphysics: images, models and "regulative ideals"

The concept of *paradeigma* gains significant philosophical depth as it becomes central to Plato's metaphysical framework¹¹. In his dialogues, *paradeigma* evolves into a technical term, best understood through the application of the pictorial metaphor to the structure of reality itself. This metaphysical expansion links *paradeigma* to the fundamental processes of creation and existence, serving as a bridge between the intelligible and sensible realms.

In Plato's dialogues, sensible realities are frequently compared to images of intelligible Forms. These images can function as corporeal mnemonic devices (ὕπομνήματα), facilitating the recollection of incorporeal realities to which sensible things bear resemblance. More profoundly, they represent the result of participation (μέθεξις)¹² – the process through which particular sensible things partake in the eternal Forms. Through participation, sensible things acquire their names and qualities in relation to their corresponding Forms, reflecting a resemblance while also exposing their inherent deficiency when compared to the pure reality of the eternal Forms. In this context, the notion of participation does not necessarily imply that a paradigm is at play, as the pictorial metaphor is limited to highlighting the similarities and ontological differences between the original and the image. The relationship between image and paradigm, as already mentioned, differs from that between original and image, as the former always involves the mediation of a third element upon which the paradigm exerts its normative function. The paradigm would not be connected to the image if an artisan (literally or metaphorically) did not take intelligible realities as a criterion and standard for their practice¹³.

The identification of Forms as *paradeigmata*¹⁴ arises when the pictorial nature of the sensible world is understood as the outcome of a productive

¹¹ Cf. Pl. *Prm.* 132c12-d4. On the "scholasticization" of Platonic metaphysics according to the pictorial metaphor, see Alex. Aphr. in *Metaph.* 82.11-83.6. Also refer to Alb. *Intr.* 9.1; 2.12.1; Xenocr. fr. 50 Heinze (= Procl. in *Prm.* 888.16-19); Diog. Laert. 3.13.6-8. Cf. A. Sheppard, *Image and Analogy in Later Neoplatonism*, in T. Kobusch and M. Erler (eds.), Berlin – Boston 2002, pp. 639-647; M.G. Mouzala, *Proclus on the Forms as Paradigms in Plato's Parmenides. The Neoplatonic Response to Aristotle and Alexander of Aphrodisias' Criticisms*, «Journal of Ancient Philosophy», 16/1 (2022), pp. 115-163.

¹² According to Aristotle's testimony (*Metaph.* 987b10-13), Plato borrowed the term μέθεξις from the Pythagoreans, who instead used μίμησις to refer to the fact that entities are imitations of numbers (τὴν δὲ μέθεξιν τοῦνομα μόνον μετέβαλεν· οἱ μὲν γὰρ Πυθαγόρειοι μιμήσει τὰ ὄντα φασὶν εἶναι τῶν ἀριθμῶν, Πλάτων δὲ μεθέξει, τοῦνομα μεταβαλὼν). Cf. also Arist. *Metaph.* 991a19-991a27.

¹³ The paradigmatic language is characterized by expressions like βλέπειν εἰς/πρός. Cf. F. M. Petrucci, *Lo sguardo del demiurgo* (Timaeus 28A6-29A5) e la semantica di βλέπω nei dialoghi platonici, in F. Aronadio (ed.), Naples 2021, pp. 89-120. In fact, it makes no sense to speak of a relationship between a paradigm and, for example, shadows, reflections, dreams, or hallucinations, since in these cases there is nothing that can intentionally refer back to the original as a criterion or paradigm.

¹⁴ The notion of Socratic *definienda* as "standards" (παραδείγματα) presents a more complex issue (cf. *Euthphr.* 6e3-6; *Men.* 72c6-e2). These are understood as criteria for identifying in-

process – when the pictorial metaphor is viewed through the lens of creation and production (ποίησις)¹⁵. In the *Timaeus*, Plato likens the generated sensible cosmos to a likeness-image (εἰκόν), the product of divine craftsmanship, where the realm of intelligible realities assumes a normative role as a *paradeigma*¹⁶. The intelligible animal functions as the model according to which the entire sensible cosmos and its visible species are shaped¹⁷ – i.e. the character of the model which is transposed to the cosmos is its nature of an all-encompassing system and that of unity and uniqueness. The Demiurge, or divine craftsman, uses this paradigm to impose order upon the sensible world. The influence of this dialogue on the Platonic tradition solidified the association of *paradeigmata* with concepts such as image, copy, or replica, extending its application beyond the productive metaphor¹⁸.

In this context, the image is understood as a sensible object crafted in conformity with an intelligible or sensible model, adhering to its form (ἰδέα), capacity (δύναμις), as well as its symmetries and proportions¹⁹. Plato's dialogues serve as essential sources for exploring the significance of *paradeigmata* within the realm of the visual arts, where the relationship between model and images

stances of virtue based on the principle of Socratic “priority of definition.” For insights on the role of Forms as standards (from a gnoseological perspective) for assessing individual cases, refer to R. M. Dancy's *Plato's Introduction of Forms*, Cambridge (UK) 2004, pp. 115-133 and G. Fine's *On Ideas: Aristotle's Criticism of Plato's Theory of Forms*, Oxford – New York 2004 [1993], p. 63. Instead of translating these terms as “model” or “standard,” some scholars prefer the concept of “*pattern*.” This allows for a view of Forms – as παραδείγματα – as abstract terms rather than perfect instances. Cf. W.J. Prior, “The Concept of Παράδειγμα in Plato's Theory of Forms,” *Apeiron: A Journal for Ancient Philosophy and Science*, 17/1 (1983), pp. 33-42; R. Patterson, *Image and Reality*, pp. 16-19; 66-71; S. Broadie, *Nature and Divinity in Plato's Timaeus*, Cambridge 2012, pp. 60-83.

¹⁵ S. Broadie, *ibid.*, p. 71, distinguishes between a concept of “thick paradigm” concerning Forms, highlighting their metaphysical independence and autonomy, and the notion of “practical quiddities,” which interprets Forms as oriented toward practice (*ibid.*, pp. 80-81). From my perspective, the notion of παράδειγμα, when employed in the pictorial metaphor, is always a “practical quiddity” – the term παράδειγμα lacks meaning in relation to Forms unless it is directed toward producing effects in the world. In this light, one can interpret not only Aristotle's criticism of the assimilation of μέθεξις to the pictorial metaphor (i.e., if Forms are paradigms, what is the nature of “the producer?”), but also the debate between Proclus and Philoponus concerning the essential or accidental nature of the platonic Form as παραδείγματα (cf. n. 17).
¹⁶ Pl. *Ti.* 28a6-b2; 28c2-29b2.

¹⁷ Regarding the identification of the intelligible παράδειγμα with the νοητὸν ζῷον, see *Ti.* 30c4-31a1. For a discussion on the nature of this model, I refer to R. D. Parry, *The Intelligible World-Animal in Plato's Timaeus*, «Journal of the History of Philosophy», 29/1 (1991), pp. 13-32 e K. Thein, *The Life Forms and their Model in Plato's Timaeus*, «Rhizai» 3/2 (2006), pp. 241-273.

¹⁸ The association between image and paradigm lies behind the aporias posed by critics of the theory of Forms: the pictorial metaphor risked undermining the substantiality of Forms in favor of the sensible realities. See Alex. Aphr. *in Metaph.* 86.13-23; Dam. *in Prm.* 182.11-15; cf. W. Leszl, *Il De ideis di Aristotele e la teoria platonica delle idee*, Firenze 1975, pp. 294-297. Simplicius, drawing on Proclus (*in Prm.* 921), explicitly refers to an unrelated relationship (ἄσχετος σχέσις) to circumvent this issue. Additionally, arguments regarding the eternity of the world were also founded on the relativity of the image-paradigm relationship (cf. Plot. 3.2.1; 5.8.12.15-25; Procl. *in Prm.* 1229-1230; Philoponus, *De aet. mund.* 24.1-16).

¹⁹ Cf. Pl. *Ti.* 28a6-b2; *Soph.* 235d7-e3.

is deeply connected to philosophical ideals about order, beauty, and reality²⁰. In Plato's metaphysical framework, the successful creation of a beautiful image or replica is not guaranteed; it relies on several factors: the ontological status of the model, which is immutable and stable, free from generation and corruption; the goodness and the nature (whether human or divine) of the craftsman, whose aim is not driven by contingencies but by the will to produce functional and virtuous products (that is, "beautiful" and "good"); the craftsman's access to the type of reality chosen as the model; and their mastery of the technical-practical processes specific to their art (τέχνη). In this sense, both the philosopher and the demiurgic divinity become symbols of a poietic-artisanal practice aimed at producing a form of order – both political and cosmic – that faithfully reflects the intelligible realities, which are endowed with normative and paradigmatic value²¹.

The *Republic* represents one of the first dialogues in which Plato explicitly attributes a paradigmatic value to the intelligible realities in relation to the sensible ones²². Despite his well-known critique of mimetic arts in Book X, Plato employs a painterly-artisanal metaphor to describe philosophers as "painters of constitutions,"²³ who rely on a divine model (θείω παραδείγματι χρώμενοι)²⁴. The knowledge of eternal realities, attained through dialectics, is an essential component of political leadership. These eternal realities serve as a regulative ideal for political *praxis*, shaping not only the governance of the city but also the personal conduct of the philosopher. According to Plato, philosophers, by contemplating an ordered and eternal reality, first imitate these realities by assimilating themselves to them as closely as possible. Then, they transpose this cosmic order into the city, shaping its public and private customs according to the harmony and structure they observe in the intelligible realm. In this way, the philosopher becomes an architect of civic order, using the paradigmatic value of intelligible realities to instill the virtue of justice in the city. This idea is reinforced in Book VII, where, after a discussion on the education of future philosophers and rulers, Plato describes the final stage of the philosopher's journey: the contemplation of the Form of the Good. Upon reaching the age of fifty, philosophers refine their vision through mathematics and dialectics, culminating in their understanding of the Good. This ultimate Form serves as a model that they use to harmonize both the city and themselves, as well as

²⁰ Cf. J. J. Pollitt, *The Ancient View of Greek Art*, pp. 207-209. Pl. *Resp.* 472d; 484c; 500e; *Soph.* 236d7-e3.

²¹ Regarding the normative value of the intelligible realities, see M. Isnardi Parente, *Platone e la prima Accademia di fronte al problema delle idee degli artefacta*, «Rivista Critica di Storia della Filosofia», 19/2 (1964), pp. 123-158.

²² In the *Phaedrus*, *Symposium*, and *Phaedo*, the pictorial metaphor does not pertain to the realm of production; therefore, there is no reference to the Forms as παραδείγματα.

²³ Pl. *Resp.* 501a-c. For the use of pictorial metaphors, see I. Männlein-Robert, *Mit Blick auf das Göttliche oder Mimesis für Philosophen in Politeia und Nomoi*, in J. Pfefferkorn & A. Spinelli (eds.), Baden-Baden 2021, pp. 168-177; Z. Petraki, *Sculpture, weaving, and the body in Plato*, Berlin-Boston 2023, pp. 114-118.

²⁴ Pl. *Resp.* 500e3.

individual citizens (καὶ ἰδόντας τὸ ἀγαθὸν αὐτό, παραδείγματι χρωμένους ἐκείνῳ, καὶ πόλιν καὶ ἰδιώτας καὶ ἑαυτοὺς κοσμεῖν)²⁵. The Idea of Good, thus, becomes the ultimate paradigm for political and ethical order.

However, this is not the only interpretation of *paradeigma* in the *Republic*, and it even seems to stand in contrast to the explicit objectives outlined in the dialogue. In the previous case, the term *paradeigma* is understood as a criterion or standard (i.e., the intelligible realities) that philosophers must refer to in order to cultivate both civic and private virtue through their political engagement. Yet the dialogue does not center on the feasibility of this political vision – on whether philosophers will genuinely assume power. The core issue was not the potential establishment or practical realization of the *kallipolis*, but rather the attainment of a moral standard: a benchmark that the just individual must strive to embody and approximate, using it as a guiding reference to attain an outcome akin to that of the perfectly just person – namely, happiness²⁶. In this sense, Plato presents two layers of *paradeigmata*: one as a practical guide for creating, akin to painters and sculptors, a just city, and the other as a moral standard for personal justice and virtue.

We wished to fix our eyes upon them as types and models [ἵνα εἰς ἐκείνους ἀποβλέποντες], so that whatever we discerned in them of happiness or the reverse would necessarily apply to ourselves [ἀναγκάζομεθα καὶ περὶ ἡμῶν ὁμολογεῖν] in the sense that whosoever is likest them will have the allotment most like to theirs. Our purpose was not to demonstrate the possibility of the realization of these ideals. (*Resp.* V, 472c9-d3; tr. Shorey)

Justice, when established as the model of the perfectly just city, does not need to be fully realized in the physical world; rather, it serves as a regulative ideal that guides both individual and collective conduct. The pragmatic significance of the *Republic* lies in its creation, through λόγος (reasoned discourse), of an ideal model of the perfectly just city (παράδειγμα ἐποιοῦμεν λόγῳ ἀγαθῆς πόλεως, 482d9-10) and the perfectly just individual, along with their opposites. This model, though inherently unattainable in its purest form, provides a criterion for those who *aspire* to achieve justice and engage in true politics. This notion marks one of the earliest instances of the “ideal-regulative” concept of *paradeigma*. In this sense, a paradigm is something that cannot be fully realized in the material and sensible world, but functions as a guiding and aspirational standard toward which individuals and societies can continually *strive*²⁷. In practice, *paradeigmata*

²⁵ Pl. *Resp.* 540a4-b5.

²⁶ The argumentative movement transitions from justice in a larger context (the city) to a smaller context (the individual), drawing out the concept of justice from their mutual interaction. Subsequently, it aims to solidify justice “within ourselves” (καὶ φανεράν γενομένην βαβειωσαίμεθ’ ἂν αὐτήν παρ’ ἡμῶν αὐτοῖς, 435a3-4). The first movement pertains to the fictional nature of the dialogue, specifically regarding the concept of the city as produced within the λόγος. The second movement, on the other hand, is practical: it transitions from the model articulated through discourse to individual practice.

²⁷ Cf. Pl. *Leg.* 739e1-4.

traditionally guided the creation of replicas in artistic or productive activities. Plato, however, extends this concept: in his philosophy, the artificial realization of a divine model²⁸ – through *logos*, or reasoned dialogue – suffices. This is analogous to a painter crafting a model of human beauty unconcerned with whether such an ideal can ever be perfectly embodied in the real world.

Do you think, then, that he would be any the less a good painter, who, after portraying a pattern of the ideally beautiful man and omitting no touch required for the perfection of the picture, should not be able to prove, that it is actually possible for such a man to exist? (*Resp.* V, 472d4-9; tr. Shorey).

The paradigm's normative and directive power does not depend on its full manifestation. Plato's city, much like the painter's ideal figure, serves as a conceptual guide for approximating justice within human affairs, regardless of whether it is ever fully instantiated. In this way, the role of *paradeigmata* in Plato's thought underscores the aspirational function of the ideal rather than its practical realization. This framework allows for the pursuit of justice as a continuous striving toward a model that, while unattainable in its pure form, remains a constant and guiding standard for ethical and political life.

3. A philosophical methodology: inquiring through paradigms

In Plato's philosophy, the significance of paradigms extends beyond their metaphysical role in the relationship between image and model, taking on essential functions in didactic and educational contexts as well. Beyond encapsulating notions like "model," "criterion," and "standard," *paradeigmata* also operate as "examples" in discursive, rhetorical, and argumentative contexts²⁹. Typically, a *paradeigma* serves as an exemplification – a concrete instance that represents

²⁸ Pl. *Resp.* 592a7-b4. ἐν οὐρανῷ παράδειγμα ἀνάκειται stands in direct contrast (ἀλλά) to τῆ ἐν λόγοις κειμένη and delves deeper into the notion of the "inner" constitution of the just man (590e; ἀποβλέπων πρὸς τὴν ἐν αὐτῷ πολιτείαν, 591e1). In other words, even though it exists in the λόγοι and nowhere on earth, this does not prevent it from being situated "in the heavens" as a παράδειγμα for those who wish to see it and inhabit it (ἑαυτὸν κατοικίσειν, b2). The implication of defining this πόλις as a celestial παράδειγμα is that it serves as the model most closely aligned with the order of intelligible realities, based on which the just man acts politically. This does not entail, for instance, equating the *kallipolis* with a specific Form. For a discussion on this aspect, I refer to Burnyeat's work, *Utopia and Fantasy: the Practicability of Plato's Ideally Just City*, in G. Fine (ed.), Oxford – New York 1999, pp. 297-300. For a commentary on the passage, see J. Adam, *The Republic of Plato. Vol. 2: Books VI-X and Indexes*, New York 2009, p. 370. Regarding the enduring theme of the "inner constitution" and the celestial city, refer to Shorey (ed.), *Plato: The Republic, II (Books VI-X)*, Cambridge (MA) – London 1942, pp. 414-415. Vegetti's interpretation, oriented politically, is presented in *La Repubblica*, Milan 2014, p. 208; Id., *Quindici lezioni su Platone*, Turin 2003.

²⁹ Cf. Pl. *Lach.* 187a7 (the example is used with a probative function, illustrating how a specific case can provide evidence in an argument). Similarly, the expression παραδείματος ἕνεκα (cf. es. *Leg.* 735c4) highlights the rhetorical use of examples to support reasoning.

an abstract or general concept – or as a particular case that aids in clarifying otherwise abstract or complex ideas³⁰. Within the dialogues, *paradeigmata* fulfill a pragmatic purpose: by introducing an example, the speaker aims to provide the interlocutor with specific instances that make abstract concepts more accessible and comprehensible.

In the *Sophist*, *paradeigmata* assume a central role in the Eleatic Stranger's research methodology, particularly within the processes of collection (συναγωγή) of the sought object (the *definiendum*) to a genus (γένος) from which to begin the division. Given the difficulty of directly identifying the object of definition³¹, the paradigm proves essential, offering a tool that, through its similarity to the *definiendum*, facilitates recognizing a shared genus (γένος) between the example (*illustrans*) and the subject being defined (*illustrandum*)³². In the first division, the Stranger introduces the fisherman as a paradigm to associate the sophist with the broader genus of acquisitive arts, thus moving the division process forward. Although the fisherman model is eventually set aside, its purpose is evident: it provides a more accessible case (εὔγνωστον) that offers a practical model to navigate the more complex inquiry concerning the sophist (218d5-6). The analysis is directed toward something less significant to obtain a model for what is more important. Here, the previously discussed link between visibility and normativity reappears. As a methodological tool³³, the *paradeigma* enables comparison between a known, visible reality and a lesser-known one, in which

³⁰ In *Soph.* 226c2, the Stranger lists various domestic activities, such as filtering, sifting, straining, winnowing, carding, weaving, and spinning, to *exemplify* diacritical activity. He aims to show (δηλώσαι) that each of these activities shares a common quality (ποῖον) – indicating that there is one overarching art present in all of them (μίαν οὔσαν ἐν ἅπασι τέχνην, 226c5-6). Additionally, in *Soph.* 251a7, Theaetetus's request for an example stems from the abstract nature of the concept of “calling the same thing by many names.” This highlights how examples can clarify complex ideas by providing concrete illustrations. Similarly, in *Republic* 559a8-9, Socrates proposes the idea of selecting examples for both necessary and non-necessary desires to help clarify these concepts in a more manageable way (Προελώμεθα δὴ τι παράδειγμα ἑκατέρων αἱ εἰσιν, ἵνα τύπῳ λάβωμεν αὐτάς).

³¹ The reference here should be understood as the “multiple appearances” of the sophist (*Soph.* 226a6; 231b10-c1).

³² Both are considered as “related in kind” (συγγενῆ) to the acquisitive art (κτητική τέχνη) (221d8-9). Regarding the role of similarity in the Stranger's method, see V. Goldschmidt, *Le Paradigme dans la dialectique platonicienne*, Vrin, Paris 1985, pp. 16ff. In particular, what I refer to here as *illustrans* and *illustrandum* is a rearticulation of the division between “*sujet majeur*” and “*sujet mineur*,” which closely aligns with the language used by the Stranger. For further exploration of this function of the paradigm, see also E. E. Pender, *Images of Persons Unseen. Plato's Metaphors for the Gods and the Soul*, Sankt Augustin 2000, pp. 7-9; 47-59; G. E. R. Lloyd, *Polarity and Analogy, Two Types of Argumentation in Early Greek Thought*, Cambridge 1966, pp. 397-403; D. El Murr, *Savoir et gouverner. Essai sur la science politique platonicienne*, Paris 2014, pp. 45-74.

³³ Cf. V. Goldschmidt, *Le Paradigme dans la dialectique platonicienne*, p. 21.

a resemblance is perceived³⁴. In this way, the fisherman becomes a normative criterion that structures the inquiry into the nature of the sophist³⁵.

In the *Politicus*, the Stranger delves into the “nature” (φύσις) of the *paradeigma* itself, thereby opening up the possibility of grasping its formal aspects within his philosophical method. This investigation also highlights the didactic and heuristic roles of the *paradeigma*, particularly when viewed as a philosophical exercise and a preparatory step for dialectical analysis.

Is this, then, a satisfactory definition, that an example is formed [ὄτι παραδειγματός γ' ἐστὶ τότε γένεσις] when that which is the same in some second unconnected thing is rightly conceived and compared with the first [ὄν ταῦτόν ἐν ἑτέρῳ διεσπασμένῳ δοξαζόμενον ὀρθῶς καὶ συναχθὲν περὶ ἐκάτερον], so that the two together form one true idea? (*Pol.* 278c4-8; tr. Fowler)

This definition is provided by the Stranger at the conclusion of a meta-model, a model used to conceptualize the model itself. The function of *paradeigmata*, as outlined by the Stranger, is closely tied to the exercise of learning. The situation described involves children who, after gaining some familiarity with the alphabet, can distinguish each letter within simpler, shorter syllables but struggle to recognize the same letters when they appear in more complex combinations, which they have not yet encountered. In this context, the known letters become *paradeigmata* because, through comparison, the children can recognize the same likeness and nature of the letter in both different combinations (τὴν αὐτὴν ὁμοιότητα καὶ φύσιν ἐν ἀμφοτέραις οὖσαν ταῖς συμπλοκαῖς, 278b 1-2). Here, the easier and more familiar combinations serve as the criteria and standards by which the unknown combinations are compared. The *paradeigma* bridges the gap from what is known to what is not yet (fully) known, facilitating the recognition of a form of similarity or identity within difference³⁶.

The reflection on models is crucial for understanding the philosophical significance of the method outlined in the *Politicus*. Throughout the dialogue,

³⁴ As noted by Goldschmidt (*ibid.*, p. 34; 83), the mechanism through which the paradigm operates in the case of the fisherman is the *translatio*, meaning a form of metaphor. In this sense, Goldschmidt sees the use of paradigms as a reconfiguration of the pictorial metaphor, where visible realities are used as tools to perceive invisible realities. At other times, paradigms take the form of a genuine “system of similarities,” as in the case of the weaving model. Here, the paradigm leans more toward analogy than metaphor («The paradigm is a complex whose structure is analyzed by establishing relationships [...] that are applied to the “major subject” to discover, not the kind, but the structure» *ibid.*, p. 36). In this way, paradigms would help to discern structures or patterns in sensible things that are directly applicable to incorporeal realities (*ibid.*, p. 92).

³⁵ This method is fundamentally aimed at progressing through trial and error, as new models can always be introduced as foundations for the συναγωγή. For instance, the dominant παράδειγμα in the *Sophist* is not that of the acquisitive art, but rather the παράδειγμα σαφέστερον (233d3) of the mimetic *eidos*, which serves as the basis for arriving at the final definition of the sophist.

³⁶ E. E. Pender, *Images of Persons Unseen*, pp. 49-50.

the Stranger and the young Socrates initially attempt to discern the nature of the political ruler using great examples (μέγαρα παραδείγματα, 277b4), such as the model of the divine shepherd. However, they later shift to discover it through a small example (έν σμικρῷ παραδείγματι, 278e6-7), progressing from smaller things (ἀπ' ἐλαττόνων) toward a reality of greater importance³⁷. In this context, the Stranger's methodological, or dialectical, use of paradigms emerges as an alliance between word and image³⁸. The similarity between the art of weaving and political art – specifically, the recognition of something identical (ταυτόν)³⁹ in both – is not conveyed merely through myth⁴⁰. Instead, it is argued through an extended discourse that constructs a verbal portrait of the ruler (277a), rather than relying on a sensible resemblance⁴¹. Vividness (ένάργεια, 277c3) – the clarity in defining the political ruler – is achieved not through physical pigments (the realm of μῦθος), but through the “colors” of rational discourse. In this way, the Stranger seems to unveil the function of the dialectical *paradeigma* as a systematic analogy, one that can be rationally justified. This approach distinguishes it from a purely visual image, which might fail to adequately represent the essence of what is being depicted⁴².

³⁷ On the “language of size”, see *ibid.*, p. 54, n. 118.

³⁸ Even when determined verbally, paradigms continue to retain a matrix of a sensible order (cf. V. Goldschmidt, *Le Paradigme dans la dialectique platonicienne*, p. 60). Pender, *Images of Persons Unseen*, pp. 56-57, distinguishes between “sensible images,” “discourse,” and “models through discourse.” Once the model serves to grasp the analogy with the major subject, it is set aside in favor of pure λόγος (*ibid.*, p. 58).

³⁹ Pl. *Pol.* 279a7-8: Τί δῆτα παράδειγμά τις ἄν, ἔχον τήν αὐτήν πολιτικῆν πραγματείαν, σμικρότατον παραθέμενος ἰκανῶς ἂν εὔροι τὸ ζητούμενον.

⁴⁰ Pl. *Pol.* 268d5-276e13.

⁴¹ I believe this point is reinforced in 285e: certain things naturally possess easily recognizable sensible similarities (αἰσθηταί τινες ὁμοιότητες), which makes it straightforward to use an image to illustrate their resemblance (e.g., a portrait and its subject). In this case, I think it pertains to the relationship between the divine shepherd (the model proposed by the great myth as a sensible image) and the human shepherd as a political figure (the reference for that picture). In other words, the great myth serves merely as a demonstration of a non-dialectical use of the παράδειγμα in contrast to the model of weaving. For the interpretation of this challenging passage, I refer to C. J. Rowe, *Plato: Statesman*, Aris & Phillips, Warminster 1995, pp. 210-212.

⁴² According to E.E. Pender, *Images of Persons Unseen*, p. 71, this distinction serves to differentiate between παράδειγμα and verbal image: while the former can be tested and is useful for uncovering a structural similarity between two entities, the latter merely suggests a similarity between two subjects. A verbal εἰκόν only points out certain resemblances, whereas a παράδειγμα exemplifies a system of similarities. For example, in Pl. *Pol.* 297e8, the comparison of royal rulers to ship captains and physicians are termed εἰκόνες, while the analogy between royal activity and weaving constitutes a παράδειγμα (279a). Goldschmidt (*Le Paradigme dans la dialectique platonicienne*, p. 112) further notes that the difference between an image and a paradigm is that the former involves a distortion of the Form, whereas the latter presents a structure that can be directly applied to the Form itself.

4. Deliberating through resemblance: the function of rhetorical paradigms and their temporality in Aristotle's *Rhetoric*

In the previous section, the methodological and argumentative significance of the term *paradeigma* was highlighted as a means of guiding from a known case or reality to an unknown one through resemblance or analogy. In that context, authority is typically exercised by the teacher, who encourages a young disciple to follow the chosen paradigm to practice dialectics or understand a complex reality. However, learning cases are not the only area where paradigms demonstrate their importance. In the realm of rhetoric, the significance of paradigms becomes even more pronounced⁴³. Especially from the Aristotelian tradition onward, *paradeigma* became a technical term designating a rhetorical tool or a form of argumentation. In rhetoric manuals *paradeigma* is often accompanied by comparisons (εἰκόνες), fables (λόγοι), or parables (παραβολαί). While these elements may sometimes be viewed as forms of *virtutes elocutionis* (ἀρεταὶ τῆς λέξεως), they are more broadly understood as methods of persuasive argumentation (πίστις; *probatio*). Sometimes, their main purpose is not just to convince the audience of a certain thesis, but also to encourage either imitation or deterrence, thereby positioning the *paradeigma* both as a rhetorical tool and as a “model” for actions⁴⁴.

Considering the various uses of examples in rhetoric, we can distinguish different functions of paradigms. First and foremost, a paradigm can serve to support – thus reinforcing and substantiating – a specific thesis (whether

⁴³The topic has been the subject of numerous studies. For this, I refer to the following works: K. Alewell, *Über das rhetorische ΠΑΡΑΔΕΙΓΜΑ: Theorie, Beispielsammlungen, Verwendung in der römischen Literatur der Kaiserzeit*, Leipzig 1913; H. Kornhardt, *Exemplum. Eine bedeutungsgeschichtliche Studie*, Diss. Göttingen 1936; B.J. Price, *Παράδειγμα and Exemplum in Ancient Rhetorical Theory*, Diss. University of California 1975; M.H. McCall, *Ancient Rhetorical Theories of Simile and Comparison*, Cambridge (MA) 1969, pp. 25-27; 59-61; 64-65; 78-79; 90-91; 94-98; 180-198; 253-256; S. Consigny, *The rhetorical example*, «Southern Speech Communication Journal», 41/2, 1976, pp. 121-132; K. Demoen, *A Paradigm for the Analysis of Paradigms: The Rhetorical Exemplum in Ancient and Imperial Greek Theory*, «Rhetorica: A Journal of the History of Rhetoric», 15/2, 1997, pp. 125-158. On the issue of the historical-practical value of παράδειγμα/*exemplum*, the essential study is P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik. Das rhetorische Exemplum. Von der Antike zur Neuzeit und die historiae im „Policraticus“ Johanns von Salisbury*, Hildesheim – Zürich – New York 1996.

⁴⁴I borrow these categories from K. Demoen, *A Paradigm for the Analysis of Paradigms*, p. 130. Naturally, the distinction between the probative-confirmatory function and the moral function of the παράδειγμα is not so clear-cut and tends to overlap depending on the pragmatic context (cf. P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik*, pp. 67-68, n. 164). Cf. Tryph. *Trop.* 200.21-23: παράδειγμά ἐστι τοῦ προγεγονότος πράγματος παρένθεσις καθ' ὁμοιότητα τῶν ὑποκειμένων πρὸς παραίνεσιν προτροπῆς ἢ ἀποτροπῆς ἔνεκεν [An example is the insertion of a past event, presented due to the similarity of subjects, with the purpose of advising (i.e., parenetic) in view of an exhortation or a dissuasion]; Polyb. Sard. *Fragmenta de figuris* 107.11-12: Παράδειγμα δέ ἐστι λόγος διὰ τῆς ὁμοίων παραθέσεως προτροπῆν ἢ ἀποτροπῆν ἢ ἀπόδειξιν τινῶν ἔχων [An example is a speech that, through the comparison of similar things, aims at exhortation, dissuasion, or demonstration]. Manieri emphasizes the parenetic aspect of the paradigm in *La terminologia della similitudine nella retorica greca di epoca tarda*, «Quaderni Urbinati di Cultura Classica», 118/1, 2018, p. 98.

prescriptive, descriptive or predictive) put forth by the speaker, convincing the audience that the described reality or the prescribed norm accurately reflects or meets the current situation. Additionally, as already mentioned, a paradigm can illustrate a general rule, an abstract concept, or an idea that would otherwise be difficult to grasp. Therefore, a primary function of *paradeigmata* is to strengthen, prove, witness, present, or illustrate a thesis for persuasive or didactic purposes. When fulfilling this role, the concept of *paradeigma* is subordinate to the universal; it makes a general rule, abstract concept, or unclear idea more visible or familiar to convince the audience of a particular thesis. In this context, rather than speaking of an analogy between the example and the general rule or abstract concept, it is more appropriate to describe this relationship in terms of instantiation⁴⁵. The example is not merely similar to another reality; it is a particular and concrete instance – more immediate, evident, and familiar – of an abstract type. For this reason, a paradigm is typically presented after the general rule when it serves as its testimony (παραδείγματος χάριν; ἔνεκα)⁴⁶.

Aristotle, however, recognizes the *paradeigma* as having a unique role in persuasion, particularly within deliberative rhetoric, where it serves as a powerful tool to motivate the audience toward action. In this context, a *paradeigma* functions as a model for behavior because the scenario it presents is directly linked to the situation being deliberated by the audience. The rhetorical process here is focused on the individual case, using the universal only as a form of mediation⁴⁷. The argument begins with a specific instance – the *illustrans*, which acts as the model – and moves toward another individual case concerning the audience – the *illustrandum*. A similarity⁴⁸ is established between these two cases, by connecting the *illustrandum* to the same universal concept of which the example is an instance. Given its familiarity and resemblance to the present scenario, the chosen *paradeigma* prompts the audience to either imitate or avoid a particular course of action. It draws upon what is already known to indicate how one should or should not behave in the current situation, which mirrors the one depicted in the example. Typically referencing a known action from the past, the speaker suggests how the audience might act in the present, thereby making the *paradeigma* directly relevant to their decision-making. This close

⁴⁵ K. Demoen, *A Paradigm for the Analysis of Paradigms*, p. 136, n. 36.

⁴⁶ Aristotle states that when it is possible to provide an enthymeme, the παράδειγμα (example) serves as a witness (μαρτύριον) and is used as a conclusion or epilogue (*Rhet.* 1394a9-11). In this case, the example's role is to support or corroborate a thesis, meaning that even a single testimony is sufficient.

⁴⁷ On the issue of the “mediation” (whether from part to part or from part to whole to part), see G. A. Hauser, *The Example in Aristotle's Rhetoric: Bifurcation or Contradiction?*, «Philosophy & Rhetoric» 1/2 (1968), pp. 78-90, and S. Consigny, *The rhetorical example*, who advocate for an “unmediated view.” For critiques of this stance, refer to W.L. Benoit, *Aristotle's example: The rhetorical induction*, in «Quarterly Journal of Speech», 66/2 (1980), pp. 182-192.

⁴⁸Cf. Arist. *Rhet.* 1394a5 (τὸ ὁμοιον ὁρᾶν). Cf. also *Rhet.* 1357b26-29: παράδειγμα δὲ ὅτι ἐστὶν ἐπαγωγή [...] ἔστι δὲ οὔτε ὡς μέρος πρὸς ὅλον οὔθ' ὡς ὅλον πρὸς μέρος οὔθ' ὡς ὅλον πρὸς ὅλον, ἀλλ' ὡς μέρος πρὸς μέρος, ὁμοιον πρὸς ὁμοιον; *Rhet.* 1360a5 – specifically regarding the deliberative genre (ἀπὸ γὰρ τῶν ὁμοίων τὰ ὁμοια γίνεσθαι πέφυκεν).

relationship between *paradeigmata* and deliberative rhetoric underscores their moral significance and highlights their temporal dimension: moving from past examples to present decisions, and ultimately shaping the future. When the *paradeigma* is used as a model, it engages the audience on a deeper, existential level, drawing from their own experiences and knowledge to guide their choices.

Aristotle views *paradeigmata* as the rhetorical equivalent of induction (ἐπαγωγή) or, more broadly, as a type of rhetorical induction⁴⁹. Unlike an inductive syllogism, however, rhetorical induction does not require a complete enumeration of individual cases. Its purpose is not scientific but practical⁵⁰. The purpose of using *paradeigmata* is not to guide the audience toward recognizing a universal proposition or absolute truth. Rather, a rhetorician employs them to persuade the audience – such as the Athenians – to adopt a specific stance. For instance, the speaker might argue that it is wrong to wage war against the Thebans. Through persuasive argumentation, the speaker guides the audience to conclude that they should refrain from waging war against the Thebans by implying that it is generally wrong to wage war against neighboring states, drawing on examples of similar cases (τούτου δὲ πίστις ἐκ τῶν ὁμοίων)⁵¹. To illustrate this, the speaker could point to the detrimental consequences the Thebans faced when they waged war against their neighbors, the Phocians. In this scenario, the orator is not attempting to scientifically prove the universal claim that “waging war against neighbors is wrong,” nor is the goal to convince the audience of this universal truth directly. Rather, the objective is to instill a belief in the audience and to apply this belief to the specific situation at hand, thereby guiding their deliberation. The purpose of using *paradeigmata*, therefore, is to transition from one individual case to another, with the universal serving as a form of mediation.

From this description, it follows that both the *paradeigma* and the situation to which the example is applied can be regarded as parts (μέρη) of the same genus (the same general concept), understood as a whole (ὅλον). The example itself is considered more familiar (γνωριμώτερον)⁵² as it arises from a past experience or is otherwise known to the audience. This relationship facilitates a kind of induction (ἐπαγωγή) in which the *illustrandum* is subsumed under the same

⁴⁹ Arist. *Rhet.* 1356b4-5 (παράδειγμα δὲ ἐπαγωγὴν ῥητορικὴν).

⁵⁰ The distinction between syllogism based on induction (ὁ ἐξ ἐπαγωγῆς συλλογισμὸς) and the example (παράδειγμα) is clarified in Aristotle's *Prior Analytics* 22-23. In *An. Pr.* 68b28-29, Aristotle notes that induction proceeds through all instances (ἢ γὰρ ἐπαγωγή διὰ πάντων), meaning that inductive reasoning seeks to encompass all relevant cases. In contrast, *παράδειγμα* relies on a specific example or a set of examples without needing to cover every instance, thus functioning more practically in rhetorical argumentation. For more on these topics, refer to: F. Piazza, *La Retorica di Aristotele. Introduzione alla lettura*, Rome 2008, pp. 115-119; Ead., *Pisteis in Comparison: Examples and Enthymemes in the Rhetoric to Alexander and in Aristotle's Rhetoric*, «Rhetorica», 19/3 (2011), pp. 309-312; C. Natali, *Paradeigma: The Problems of Human Acting and the Use of Examples in Some Greek Authors of the 4th Century B.C.*, «Rhetoric Society Quarterly», 19/2 (1989), pp. 144-147; W. L. Benoit, *Aristotle's example*, p. 188.

⁵¹ Arist. *An. Pr.* 69a4-5.

⁵² Arist. *Rhet.* 1357b29-30; Cf. *An. Pr.* 69a16.

genus as the *illustrans*. In other words, by employing an example, the speaker enables the audience to recognize an analogy or similarity between an event that has already occurred and the current situation. This recognition encourages the audience to deliberate.

Among the various cases of persuasive argumentation through *paradeigmata*, Aristotle also mentions Dionysius' (possible) aspiration to tyranny, supposedly foreshadowed by his request for a personal bodyguard⁵³. In the situation described, it is not yet clear whether Dionysius, through his request for a bodyguard, truly intends to become a tyrant. However, a rhetorician aiming to persuade the audience of this possibility – and thus motivate them to take action, namely, to oppose Dionysius' request – could effectively employ *paradeigmata* from history. For instance, the speaker might cite the behaviors of Pisistratus and Theagenes, both of whom similarly requested bodyguards while conspiring toward tyranny. By highlighting this resemblance, the speaker treats the *paradeigmata* (the historical examples of Pisistratus and Theagenes) and Dionysius' case as two instances, or two “parts” (μέρη) of the same genus, namely, the general notion that “those who aspire to tyranny request a bodyguard.”⁵⁴ In this rhetorical maneuver, the orator performs a type of induction, inferring from these known cases that those who have requested a bodyguard in the past have aspired to tyranny. As a result, the current situation involving Dionysius is subsumed under this broader generalization. However, the goal of persuasion through *paradeigmata* is not to establish a universal truth; rather, it is to suggest to the audience that it is quite likely that Dionysius, too, harbors tyrannical ambitions. Therefore, they should act to prevent him from securing a bodyguard⁵⁵.

The form of persuasive argumentation through *paradeigmata* thus assumes a fundamentally practical role. As previously mentioned, Aristotle considers *paradeigmata* particularly suited to deliberative speeches (δημηγορικώτερα, 1418a; συμβουλευτικοί, 1368a27)⁵⁶. The primary function of deliberative rhetoric is, in fact, to influence decision-making processes that concern the future and the means of securing what is beneficial for the community⁵⁷.

⁵³ Arist. *Rhet.* 1357b30ff.

⁵⁴ Arist. *Rhet.* 1357b35-36: πάντα δὲ ταῦτα ὑπὸ τὸ αὐτὸ καθόλου, ὅτι ὁ ἐπιβουλεύων τυραννίδι φυλακὴν αἰτεῖ.

⁵⁵ Based on similarity, this type of argumentation can naturally be countered through counter-examples (by presenting another example, equally well-known, that invalidates the first) or by highlighting how the similarity between the two situations is inappropriate. See K. Demoen, *A Paradigm for the Analysis of Paradigms*, p. 137. A classification of the types of similarity is found in Quintilian's *Institutio Oratoria* 5.11.5-14.

⁵⁶ Cf. Lyc. 83.1-4: βούλομαι δὲ μικρὰ τῶν παλαιῶν ὑμῖν διελθεῖν, οἷς παραδείγμασι χρώμενοι καὶ περὶ τούτων καὶ περὶ τῶν ἄλλων βέλτιον βουλεύσεσθε; 124.5-6: τὸ γὰρ μετὰ πολλῶν παραδειγμάτων διδάσκειν ῥαδίαν ὑμῖν τὴν κρίσιν καθίστησι.

⁵⁷ Arist. *Rhet.* 1358b8-9. The “deliberative” genre of rhetoric (συμβουλευτικόν) is based on exhortation or dissuasion (προτροπή and ἀποτροπή) and focuses on the future – since those who offer counsel do so by urging or dissuading regarding future events. Moreover, one can deliberate only about things that are possible (1359a30-34). On the relationship between συμβουλευτικόν and deliberation concerning means, cf. *Rhet.* 1362a15ff. In general, rhetoric itself naturally has a connection with the deliberative sphere (*Rhet.* 1357a).

When the *paradeigma* fulfills this function, it can rightly be conceived of as a model for conduct. The model is familiar to the audience, resonating with their experiences and concerns – it touches them intimately⁵⁸. It is inherently action-oriented, as the rhetor presents a case that serves as a lesson from which a form of moral instruction can be derived. The rhetorical strength of this process lies in the orator's ability to guide the audience from what is already known to the unknown, from actions that have already been performed to decisions that are yet to be made, and from past experiences to future possibilities.

Speaking generally, of the topics common to all rhetorical arguments, amplification is most suitable for epideictic speakers [...], examples are most suitable for deliberative speakers, for it is by examination of the past that we divine and judge the future [ἐκ γὰρ τῶν προγεγονότων τὰ μέλλοντα καταμαντευόμενοι κρίνομεν] (*Rhet.* 1368a26-31; tr. Freese)

The *paradeigma* is, therefore, not merely a rhetorical embellishment; it is a powerful persuasive tool that prompts action based on the belief that the past can instruct the present, and that the similarity between past and present can serve as a guide for the future⁵⁹. By virtue of its accessibility or familiarity, an individual case from the past acquires normative value for present action, as it bears a resemblance to current circumstances. When used as a model for action, the *paradeigma* goes beyond mere didactic illustration or probative testimony. It carries an orientational function, guiding the audience not only to understand a concept but to act upon it. In Aristotle's view, the most authentic examples are those drawn from events that have already occurred (τὸ λέγειν πράγματα προγενομένα)⁶⁰. For instance, if one seeks to persuade the audience that they must prepare to defend against the Great King and prevent him from conquering Egypt, one should emphasize the historical fact that Darius and Xerxes previously conquered Egypt before advancing into Greece⁶¹. By invoking past events, the speaker establishes a pattern that the audience can recognize and relate to their current situation.

However, when a speaker does not have access to a repertoire of known and past events, they may naturally invent some. To convince the audience of

⁵⁸ Typically, the period from which παραδείγματα are drawn for deliberative oratory pertains to recent rather than distant history. In Thucydides historical *exempla* rarely go back before the Persian Wars, as these examples must hold an existential value for the audience. See J. C. Iglesias Zoido, *Paradigma y entimema: el ejemplo histórico en los discursos deliberativos de Tucídides*, «Emerita», LXV/1 (1997), pp. 5-8.

⁵⁹ The aim of the deliberative genre of rhetoric is the beneficial and the harmful (τὸ σύμφερον καὶ βλαβερόν, *Rhet.* 1358b22).

⁶⁰ Cf. Quintilian, *Inst.* 5.11.6.2-5: «Among the instruments of this kind, the most powerful is what we properly call an *exemplum*, that is, the recall of a fact that has actually occurred or is presented as such, useful for persuading regarding what one intends to prove. [*Potentissimum autem est inter ea quae sunt huius generis quod proprie uocamus exemplum, id est rei gestae aut ut gestae utilis ad persuadendum id quod intenderis commemoratio*].»

⁶¹ Arist. *Rhet.* 1393a32-b4.

a particular thesis and prompt action, comparisons (παραβολαί)⁶² or fables (λόγοι) can be created, allowing the use of fictional, hypothetical, or even imaginary situations as *paradeigmata*⁶³. Regarding the difference between fables and historical examples, Aristotle adds that while both serve to illustrate a point and persuade an audience, they function in distinct ways. A fable often presents a moral lesson through a story featuring animals or inanimate objects that personify human traits. It conveys its message through allegory and imaginative scenarios, which can resonate on a moral or ethical level. In contrast, a historical example typically draws on more relatable, concrete situations that can be directly linked to the audience's experiences or to well-known historical events.

Fables are suitable for public speaking, and they have this advantage that, while it is difficult to find similar things that have really happened in the past, it is easier to invent fables; for they must be invented, like comparisons, if a man is capable of seizing the analogy; and this is easy if one studies philosophy. Thus, while the lessons conveyed by fables are easier to provide, those derived from facts are more useful for deliberative oratory, because as a rule the future resembles the past [χρησιμώτερα δὲ πρὸς τὸ βουλευσασθαι τὰ διὰ τῶν πραγμάτων ὅμοια γὰρ ὡς ἐπὶ τὸ πολὺ τὰ μέλλοντα τοῖς γεγονόσιν] (*Rhet.* 1394a2-8; tr. Freese).

5. Models of conduct: the paradigmatic use of history and the power of imitation

In the previous section, I explored the rhetorical significance of *paradeigmata*, focusing on their role in the deliberative sphere. When the *paradeigma* functions as a model for a decision-making process, it becomes especially useful for evaluating its moral implications⁶⁴. In this section, it is crucial to examine instances where the *paradeigma* implies not simply a reference to a past action or event⁶⁵, but rather involves an identification between the *exemplum* and a specific individual, thereby inspiring imitation or emulation. In this context, *paradeigmata* function as *exempla virtutis*, presenting the actions and behaviors of renowned or influential figures as either positive or negative models. By invoking these examples, a speaker can encourage the audience to imitate, emulate, or avoid certain behaviors. This use of *paradeigmata* is often integrated

⁶² Among the parables, Aristotle includes the Socratic discourses (τὰ Σωκρατικά), referring to the use of analogies or fictional situations created by Socrates in Plato's dialogues.

⁶³ Regarding the division of types of παραδείγματα, I refer to L. Spina, *Aristotele al lavoro: due note sulla Retorica*, in L. Calboli Montefusco (ed.), Roma 2008, pp. 213-238. For the relationship between παράδειγμα and other figures of similarity in rhetorical manuals, see A. Manieri, *La terminologia della similitudine nella retorica greca di epoca tarda*, pp. 97-99.

⁶⁴ Ch. Perelman & L. Olbrechts-Tyteca, *The New Rhetoric. A Treatise on Argumentation*, trans. J. Wilkinson & P. Weaver, Notre Dame – London 1969, pp. 362-370.

⁶⁵ In Aristotelian *Rhetoric*, as previously noted, parables and fables are considered types of παραδείγματα. However, it is the historical example that ultimately becomes the predominant form. For a deeper exploration of these aspects, see P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik*, pp. 54-60; K. Damoen, *A Paradigm*.

into exhortatory or protreptic (motivational) discourses, guiding moral and ethical decision-making with a strong emphasis on education.

In this case as well, the reference to *exempla* highlights a profound connection to temporality, history, and visibility. These models, rooted in the past and thus familiar to the target of the exhortation, are often drawn from the history of one's ancestors or the political heritage of one's community. Their actions, behaviors, or deeds serve as both a guide for conduct and a moral standard⁶⁶. Consequently, the past assumes a distinctly "public" and "paradigmatic" role, functioning not only as a constant point of comparison for the present but also as a rich repository of exemplary individuals and deeds that can inspire and reflect the current historical situation.

Reflecting on models of virtue is pivotal in understanding the intersection of historical consciousness, memory, and moral theory. Notably, parallels are often drawn between what can be termed "media devices of memory" – such as μνημεῖα (funerary monuments), εἰκόνες (statues), ἀναθήματα (votive offerings), and στήλαι (stelae inscribed with publicly displayed laws or decrees). When votive offerings, statues, or stelae are intended to present, depict or embody an *exemplum*, their visibility in the public sphere is essential to their paradigmatic significance⁶⁷. In this sense, rhetorical discourse transforms into an

⁶⁶The moralistic or didactic approach to historiography, along with the paradigmatic value of the past, were central themes throughout ancient historiography. From its inception, the work of the historian was seen as having a clear ὠφελία – a practical utility – not merely aimed at offering a mimetic portrayal of past events to entertain or stir emotions. For the past to be useful, it needed to be understood with discernment so it could serve as a παράδειγμα for the future. Cf. Thuc. 1.22.4; Diod. 1.1.4; Liv. 1. pr. 10; Cic. *De orat.* 2.36.1-4; Tac. *Hist.* 1.3; 3.51. For more on moralism and didacticism in ancient historiography, see G. Cerri & B. Gentili, *Le teorie del discorso storico*, Roma 1975, pp. 19-45; 61-63, and T.E. Duff, *Plutarch's Lives: Exploring Virtue and Vice*, Oxford – New York 2002, pp. 52-65.

⁶⁷Dem. 20.64: προσήκει τοίνυν τὰς στήλας ταύτας κυρίας εἶν τὸν πάντα χρόνον, ἴν', ἕως μὲν ἂν τινες ζῶσι, μηδὲν ὑφ' ὑμῶν ἀδικῶνται, ἐπειδὴν δὲ τελευτήσωσιν, ἐκεῖναι τοῦ τῆς πόλεως ἡθους μνημεῖον ὄσι, καὶ παραδείγμαθ' ἐστῶσι τοῖς βουλομένοις τι ποιεῖν ὑμᾶς ἀγαθόν, ὅσους εὖ ποιήσαντας ἡ πόλις ἀντ' εὖ πεποίηκεν [It is therefore fitting that these steles be preserved in perpetuity, so that as long as these men live, they will suffer no injustice at your hands, and when they have passed away, these steles will stand as a monument to the character of the city and serve as an example for those who wish to do good, showing that the city rewards in kind those who have acted with virtue]. The reference here is to decrees (ψηφίσματα) honoring the benefactors of Athens, which, even after their death, remain as παραδείγματα (examples) for future benefactors. Cf. also Lyc. 127.5-6: «You have both reminders and examples of their punishment, recorded in the decrees concerning those who wronged the city [ὑπομνήματα δ' ἔχετε καὶ παραδείγματα τῆς ἐκείνων τιμωρίας τὰ ἐν τοῖς περὶ τῶν ἀδικούντων ψηφίσμασιν ὠρισμένα]». The paradigmatic value of decrees and laws is primarily due to their public display and their inherent "visibility" (cf. M. Gagarin, *Writing Greek Law*, Cambridge – New York 2008, pp. 67-68; 86-87). Regarding statues as objects in public spaces that serve to showcase or remind people of examples of virtue, we must also mention the episode, cited by the orator Lysurgus, concerning the betrayal of Hipparchus (there is no consensus on his identification; cf. M. Berti, *Licurgo e il tradimento di Ipparco (Lycurg. Leoc. 117sg.)*, in M.G. Angeli Bertinelli & A. Donati (eds.), Rome 2005, pp. 401-409), whose statue was demolished and melted down to create a stele inscribed with the names of Hipparchus and the other traitors. According to Lysurgus, this act was not simply motivated by the fact that they could not access the living body of the accused and thus turned against his statue,

artfully constructed presentation of a memory deemed worthy of preservation for its moral significance. As has been observed, this process signifies a new media form – writing – that facilitates the reinterpretation of the past to extract relevant lessons or practical utility for the present⁶⁸. In conjunction with statues, memorials and steles, written speech becomes a medium for preserving both collective and individual memory, inheriting from the tradition of the poetical encomium the goal of perpetuating the glory that virtuous individuals attained during their lives.

From the Attic rhetoric of the 4th century BCE to the *exemplum virtutis* of the Roman world⁶⁹, the historical παράδειγμα evolved into a model of

destroying his memorial (τὸ μνημεῖον ἀνελόντες); instead, they melted down the statue and inscribed the names on a stele so that they would serve as παραδείγματα for future generations (Lyc. 117ff., esp. 119.5-7: οὐχ ὅπως τὸν χαλκοῦν ἀνδριάντα συγχωνεύσειαν, ἀλλ' ἵνα τοῖς ἐπιγυνομένοις παράδειγμα εἰς τὸν λοιπὸν χρόνον ὡς εἶχον πρὸς τοὺς προδότας καταλίποιεν). For the paradigmatic value of statues, see IvO 293.8-9 (the statue of Apollo as an example of good manners). Additionally, numerous inscriptions attest to votive offerings (ἀναθήματα) serving as examples of virtue (IG2².4908, a votive offering to Pan; IG2².3022 ([τ]οιάδε τις δείξας παραδε[ί]γματα παισὶν ἕατο μᾶλλον ὀρέξασθαι τῆς ἀρετῆς προτρέπει), where the offering explicitly has a protreptic purpose; IG 4².1.618 (ἀνδρείας παράδειγμα·). A particularly notable inscription is found on the statues of Heraclea (II/III century AD), which were engraved as a decree by the Achaeans (IG5.2.518: «Decree of the Achaeans. The Achaeans decided. Gellius Bassus proposed. Heracleia, daughter of Eumelos, shall be honored for her modesty and all feminine virtues with statues at every Greek festival. Also, let this decree be inscribed on a stele accompanying the statue so that the memory of Heracleia, daughter of Eumelos, may be eternal, and all other Achaian women may have an example of modesty and piety [ὅπως ἂν Ἡρακλείας Εὐμήλου ἢ μνήμη ἀίδιος εἴη καὶ παράδειγμα σωφροσύνης καὶ εὐσεβείας αἱ ἄλλαι Ἀχαϊίδες γυναῖκες ἔχοιεν]»; tr. Siekierka, Stebnicka, and Wolicki). For the eternalizing value of virtuous actions, see Isoc. Dem. 8. Cf. P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik*, p. 66 (concerning the images and busts of Roman ancestors as *exempla virtutis*); A. Lucci, *Techniques de visibilité*, pp. 58-61 (regarding statues as models for the spectacularization of ascetic practices). For the spectacularization of punishments, see Pl. Grg. 525b (where παραδείγματα are the souls of individuals who suffer terrible and atrocious punishments – such as Tantalus, Sisyphus, and Tityos – serving as θεάματα and νοθετήματα (c9-10) for the unjust, who, by observing them, may become better souls, struck by fear for their own fate. On the exemplary value of punishments, see Pl. Leg. 855a1; 862e5; Dem. 22.68.12-13; 24.218.1-5; Lys. 14.12.6-8 (ἐὰν δὲ τοὺς ἐπιφανεστάτους τῶν ἐξαμαρτανόντων τιμωρῆσθε, πάντες πεύσονται, ὡστε τοῦτῳ παραδείγματι χρώμενοι βελτίους ἔσονται οἱ πολῖται).

⁶⁸ G. Cerri and B. Gentili, *Le teorie del discorso storico*.

⁶⁹ Cf. R. Barthes, *L'ancienne rhétorique*, «Communications», 16, p. 201. The most extensive collection of *exempla* from the Latin world is Valerius Maximus's *Factorum et dictorum memorabilium libri IX*, although the concept of *exemplum* was central to Roman patriotism as a whole. The Latin *exemplum* not only pertained to moral exemplarity but was deeply tied to the “genealogical” history and patriotic celebration of the *mos maiorum*. Every descendant or successor was seen as part of an obligatory tradition, positioning themselves as both heirs of the past and models for the future. This framework meant that family histories, and by extension Roman history itself, formed chains of biographical exempla, where the living saw themselves as the latest link (P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik*, p. 71). Thus, the Roman *exemplum* went beyond simply drawing parallels between past and present situations; it held a foundational role in shaping both family and national identity. In late antiquity, the use of *exempla* became increasingly anecdotal, losing its historical grounding through a process of “intra-literary dissolution” and “de-historicization” (*ibid.*, pp. 79-81). For more on the Latin *exemplum* and its reception in patristic literature and medieval *exempla*, see C. Bremon, J. Le Goff & J.-C.

conduct. It became a crucial tool, not only for rhetorical persuasion but also for exhorting individuals to imitate models drawn from both their own history and that of others (cf. the distinction between οἰκεῖον and ἀλλότριον παράδειγμα), extracting lessons from both individual and collective actions⁷⁰. This connotation of *paradeigmata* is already evident in the works of Thucydides⁷¹ and the tragedians⁷², but it gains particular prominence in the rhetoric of the 4th century BCE⁷³. In the protreptic writings of Isocrates, the *paradeigma* as an individual model of conduct plays a central role. Isocrates often begins with the individual's familial and political history while also considering the exemplary tales and deeds of mythical heroes⁷⁴. Not surprisingly, Isocrates' orations later served as templates for the *speculum principis* literary genre, which provided political instruction for rulers⁷⁵. In his *Evagoras*, Isocrates addresses Nicocles, the son and heir of the deceased ruler of Salamis in Cyprus, offering an encomium of the father. However, this praise transcends mere flattery; it serves as a compelling call to virtue for the future ruler. The programmatic intent of this encomium is specifically to function as an *exemplum virtutis*, artfully crafted through a well-structured discourse (λόγος). In this way, Isocrates' humanistic political ideal of paideia actively engages with the values of imitation and the comparison to exemplary figures from the past.

For these reasons especially I have undertaken to write this discourse because I believed that for you, for your children, and for all the other descendants of Evagoras, it would be by far the best incentive [παράκλησιν], if someone should assemble his achievements, give them verbal adornment, and submit them to you for your contemplation and study [θεωρεῖν ὑμῖν καὶ συνδιατρίβειν αὐταῖς]. For we exhort young men to the study of philosophy by praising others in order that they, emulating those who are eulogized, may desire to adopt the same pursuits, but I appeal to you and

Schmitt, *L'«exemplum»*, Turnhout 1982, pp. 43-49; P. von Moos, *Geschichte als Topik*, pp. 48-112.

⁷⁰ C. Natali, *Paradeigma*, p. 142.

⁷¹ Thuc. 2.37.1.1-3; 3.10.6; 39.3.2; 40.7.6; 57.1.1-2; 67.6.5-6; 5.90.1.5-7; 6.77.1. On the historical *exemplum* in Thucydides see J. C. Iglesias Zoido, *Paradigma y entimema*.

⁷² Eur. *El.* 1084-85 (τὰ γὰρ κακὰ παράδειγμα τοῖς ἐσθλοῖσιν εἴσοψιν τ' ἔχει); Soph. *Oed. Tyr.* 1193.

⁷³ See K. Clarke, *Making Time for the Past Local History and the Polis*, Oxford – New York 2008, pp. 274-285; C. Natali, *Paradeigma*, pp. 147ff.; Dem. 9.41.7; 19.263.2; 276.2; 251.3; 343.8; 22.78. 1-5; Aeschin. 3.245.6-7; Andoc. 3.32.6; Lyc. 83.4-8.

⁷⁴ W. Jaeger, *Paideia: The Ideals of Greek Culture*, Vol. III: *The Conflict of Cultural Ideals in the Age of Plato*, trans. G. Highet, Oxford – New York, p. 102. Regarding historical examples in Isocrates, see G. Schitz-Kahlmann, *Das Beispiel der Geschichte im politischen Denken des Isokrates*, Leipzig 1939.

⁷⁵ On the model of speeches written for the education of rulers, the observations of W. Jaeger in *Paideia* III, pp. 84-105, remain relevant. Jaeger interprets the "protreptic" genre of Isocrates as a reworking of the poetic encomium, particularly that of Pindar. Specifically, see *ibid.*, p. 86: «Its essence was the ancient concept on which the poetic encomium was based – the noble Example» (cf. also *ibid.*, p. 100). A similar argument can be made for Xenophon's encomium of Agesilaus (cf. *Ag.* 10.2.1-4: «It seems to me that the virtue of Agesilaus is a noble example for those wishing to practice manly excellence» [καλὸν ἄν μοι δοκεῖ [εἶναι] ἡ Ἀγησιλάου ἀρετὴ παράδειγμα γενέσθαι τοῖς ἀνδραγαθίαν ἀσκεῖν βουλομένοις]).

yours, using as examples not aliens, but members of your own family [οὐκ ἄλλοτριούς παραδείγμασι χρώμενος ἀλλ' οἰκεῖοις] [...] (*Ev.* 76-77; tr. Van Hook)

This statement is particularly significant as it follows a comparison between “artistically crafted speeches” (λόγοι οἱ τεχνιχῶς ἔχουσι) – those composed by Isocrates himself – and memorials (μνημεῖα) and images of bodies (εἰκόνες τῶν σωμάτων). As previously highlighted, statues and steles may possess paradigmatic value, serving as foundational elements of collective memory prominently displayed in public spaces. In this context, Isocrates extols the pictorial capacity of rhetorical discourse, which conveys a more intricate and nuanced portrayal of moral and political virtues. It is through λόγος⁷⁶ that one can create and contemplate the images of the deeds and reasoning (τὰς τῶν πράξεων καὶ τῆς διανοίας) of virtuous individuals⁷⁷. Compared to material images, speeches are far more conducive to dissemination, serving as representations of virtue not only for those directly addressed but also for “wise men.” While it is challenging to uniform the qualities of the body in relation to the images crafted or painted, it is significantly easier to imitate (ῥᾶδιόν ἐστι μιμεῖσθαι) the customs and thoughts articulated in words (τοὺς δὲ τρόπους καὶ τὰς διανοίας). Thus, the purpose of the encomium of Evagoras is to provide an *exemplum virtutis* not only for Nicocles and his descendants – who find in their father and ancestor an οἰκεῖον παράδειγμα⁷⁸ – but also for all who aspire to rule according to virtue⁷⁹.

⁷⁶ A fundamental aspect of Isocratean preceptive teaching is the mediation of writing. See B. Gentili & G. Cerri, *Le teorie del discorso storico nel pensiero greco e la storiografia romana arcaica*, pp. 27-28.

⁷⁷ On the “contemplation” of models see Lyc. 100.1-6.

⁷⁸ On the theme of the οἰκεῖον παράδειγμα, see Isocrates' *Ad Philippum* (113. 6-7).

⁷⁹ The educational purpose of Plutarch's teachings will be similar, based on an analogous concept of παράδειγμα – see specifically *Quis Suos*, 14-15, where the function of emulation (ζῆλοσις) is outlined. Although Plutarch's *Lives* may have been directed towards public figures pursuing a political career (the imitation of great men thus serves as motivation for the future political leader), for most of Plutarch's readers, the context has changed: the role of the modern politician in the Roman Empire differed from that of their counterparts in classical times, as war and peace were no longer under their direct control (T.E. Duff, *Plutarch's Lives*, p. 67). Christopher Pelling distinguishes between “protreptic” moralism and “descriptive” moralism in his *Plutarch: Life of Antony* (Oxford – New York 1988, pp. 15-16). Protreptic moralism implicitly or explicitly contains some moral injunction meant to be put into practice. Descriptive moralism occurs in discourse that raises moral questions without striving to guide individual conduct. Plutarch's approach can thus be seen as a description of character for paradigmatic purposes without an explicit moral exhortation directed at a specific historical figure. Plutarch's interest lies in personality or character. For further reading on Plutarch's educational approach, see T.E. Duff, *Plutarch's Lives*, pp. 66-71; A. P. Jiménez, “*Exemplum*: the Paradigmatic Education of the Ruler in the Lives of Plutarch,” in P. A. Stadter & L. Van der Stockt (eds.), Leuven 2002, pp. 105-114; P. A. Stadter, *Plutarch and his Roman Readers*, New York 2014, pp. 215-230; E. Valgiglio, “Dagli ‘Ethicà’ ai ‘Bioi’ in Plutarco,” in H. Temporini et al. (eds.), *Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt (ANRW)*, Berlin – Boston 1992, pp. 3965-78; 4010-13.

In the oration *To Demonicus*, Isocrates places imitation through *exempla* at the heart of his educational framework. The speech is explicitly crafted as an exhortation (παραίνεσις, 5) with the purpose of guiding the young man on how to live his life – what goals to pursue, which actions to avoid, and what kind of people to associate with. Demonicus' father, Hipponicus, is presented as a noble model (καλὸν παράδειγμα) of virtue, and Demonicus is urged to shape his life according to this example (πρὸς ὃν δεῖ ζῆν σ' ὥσπερ πρὸς παράδειγμα, 11). Isocrates advises him to «treat his father's way of life as law and to become an imitator and emulator of his father's virtue (νόμον μὲν τὸν ἐκείνου τρόπον ἡγησάμενον, μιμητὴν δὲ καὶ ζηλωτὴν τῆς πατρῶας ἀρετῆς γιγνόμενον· 11.5-7)». The path to virtue, according to Isocrates, lies in following specific practices that he outlines in the speech, which cover the young man's relationship with religion, his conduct towards family and friends, and his personal discipline. Furthermore, Isocrates encourages Demonicus to draw lessons from the teachings of poets, sages, and “philosophers”, viewing their stories as additional *paradeigmata* to guide his behavior⁸⁰. Within this oration, Isocrates also introduces a moral and didactic perspective on history, using the concept of *paradeigma* to link historical knowledge with ethical education. As Jaeger observed, Isocrates was the first to blend historical understanding with a structured educational agenda, emphasizing that examples from the past serve as valuable guides for present conduct⁸¹.

In your deliberations, let the past be an exemplar for the future; for the unknown may be soonest discerned by reference to the known [Βουλευόμενος παραδείγματα ποιοῦ τὰ παρεληλυθότα τῶν μελλόντων· τὸ γὰρ ἀφανὲς ἐκ τοῦ φανεροῦ ταχίστην ἔχει τὴν διάγνωσιν] (34, 1-3; tr. Norlin).

⁸⁰ In the concluding sections of the protreptic (51-52), Isocrates' educational ideal is summarized, highlighting its connection to *paradeigmata* (*Dem.* 51.1-5: «You should aim to be inspired by examples of the good and beautiful [Οἷς δεῖ παραδείγμασι χρώμενόν σ' ὀρέγεσθαι τῆς καλοκαγαθίας] and not only to adhere to those we have mentioned, but also to learn the best from the poets and to read any useful insights from other sophists [ἀλλὰ καὶ τῶν ποιητῶν τὰ βέλτιστα μανθάνειν καὶ τῶν ἄλλων σοφιστῶν εἴ τι χρήσιμον εἰρήκασιν ἀναγιγνώσκειν]»). Those who aspire to a higher education must not overlook any experience but should gather all useful teachings (τὰ βέλτιστα συλλέγειν). For a discussion on Isocrates' protreptic method, see W. Jaeger, *Paideia*, III, pp. 98-99. Isocrates' educational model is grounded in the constant use of imitation and, consequently, the educational function of *paradeigmata* (*ibid.*, pp. 100-101). This applies not only to the strictly educational context but also to models of life and governance (cf. *C. Soph.* 17; *Nic.* 31.2-4; 37.5-6; *Arch.* 83.5-7; *Pac.* 49.3-6). For further reading on Isocrates' education, see R. Hariman, “Civic Education, Classical Imitation, and Democratic Polity,” in T. Poulakos & D. Depew (eds.), Austin 2004, pp. 217-234.

⁸¹ Cf. W. Jaeger, *Paideia*, III, p. 101: «Here for the first time historical writing begins to influence political thought and the general culture of the whole era. [...] And now in the *paideia* of Isocrates – especially in his programme for educating the future monarch – this mighty new intellectual instrument is fully employed for the first time, and becomes, as it was fated to, one of the most powerful tools by which man shapes his destiny and his character». For insights into Isocrates' view of history, refer to C. B. Welles, *Isocrates' View of History*, in L. Wallach (ed.), Ithaca (NY) 1966, pp. 3-25; C. D. Hamilton, *Greek Rhetoric and History: The Case of Isocrates*, in G. W. Bowersock, W. Burkert & M. C. Putnam (eds.), Berlin – Boston 1979, pp. 290-298.

Conclusion

This essay has mapped out the concept of *paradeigma* across a range of contexts to reveal its nuanced and multifaceted role in ancient thought. By examining the use of paradigms in artisanal practices, philosophy, rhetoric, and protreptics, this analysis highlights the term's diverse meanings – each unified by the dual dimensions of normativity and visibility. Rather than tracing a single, linear evolution of *paradeigmata*, this approach reveals how the concept adapts to fit distinct situations, maintaining its relevance across different domains. At its core, the normative power of a paradigm lies in its capacity to guide actions and establish moral standards. Whether as a model in craftsmanship, a rhetorical or didactic tool, or an ethical example from history, a *paradeigma* functions as a practical reference point, informing production, learning, behavior, conduct, and decision-making processes. Crucially, this normative role is not absolute; it varies according to specific needs within particular contexts, acting as a responsive guide rather than embodying a fixed truth. Visibility strengthens this normative function, as paradigms achieve their greatest impact when they are accessible, familiar, and displayed in public spaces or highlighted in rhetorical discourse. Through public memorials, statues, and rhetorical illustration, paradigms become visible and accessible, establishing themselves as moral and educational touchstones that connect the past – whether familiar or political – to present circumstances. By making an individual, event, or historical situation visibly relevant, *paradeigmata* provide structures that orient thought and action, underscoring their essential role in shaping both individual and collective conducts and decision-making processes in the present.

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